

Numerical Stability and Regression Analysis for Quadratic Radiative Casson–Williamson Trihybrid Nanofluid Flow across a Porous Shrinking Surface

By
Gopinath Mandal^{1*}, and Dulal Pal²

¹ Siksha-Satra, Visva-Bharati University, Sriniketan-731236, India

² Department of Mathematics, Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan-731235, India

*Corresponding author: Gopinath Mandal, gopi_math1985@rediffmail.com

Abstract

This study examines the flow and heat transfer characteristics of a Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid over a permeable shrinking surface, accounting for velocity slip and nonlinear (quadratic) thermal radiation. The trihybrid nanofluid, composed of Au, Zn, and Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles dispersed in a blood-based fluid, is considered to enhance thermal transport efficiency. The governing nonlinear partial differential equations are transformed into similarity equations and solved numerically using the `bvp4c` solver. The analysis reveals the existence of dual solutions within a specific range of the suction and shrinking parameters. A temporal stability analysis based on an eigenvalue formulation confirms that the upper branch solution is stable, while the lower branch solution is unstable. It is observed that increasing the suction parameter significantly enhances the skin-friction coefficient and heat transfer rate, with the Nusselt number increasing by approximately 7% over the considered range, indicating substantial improvement in thermal performance. Furthermore, the trihybrid nanofluid exhibits markedly superior heat transfer performance compared to conventional nanofluids, owing to its improved effective thermophysical properties. To ensure the reliability of the numerical results, a statistical regression analysis is conducted, yielding a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 > 0.99$), low RMSE (approximately 0.015), and highly significant F-test values ($p < 0.001$), confirming excellent agreement between predicted and computed data. A key novelty lies in the simultaneous integration of dual-solution stability analysis and statistical regression validation, which has not been reported in the existing literature. These findings highlight the combined effects of non-Newtonian behavior, nanoparticle synergy, and nonlinear radiation on heat transfer performance, offering valuable insights for advanced thermal systems and biomedical applications.

Keywords: Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid, Quadratic Thermal radiation, Velocity slip, Shrinking surface, Stability analysis, Regression analysis.

1 Nomenclature

Symbol	Description	Unit
u, v	Velocity components in x - and y -directions	m s^{-1}
x, y	Cartesian coordinates along and normal to the surface	m
t	Time	s
T	Fluid temperature	K
T_w	Wall temperature	K
T_∞	Ambient temperature	K
θ	Dimensionless temperature	–
η	Similarity variable	–
f	Dimensionless stream function	–
τ	Dimensionless time variable	–
τ_{ij}	Shear stress tensor	Pa
p_y	Yield stress	Pa
μ	Dynamic viscosity of base fluid	Pa s
μ_{thnf}	Effective dynamic viscosity of trihybrid nanofluid	Pa s
ρ_f	Density of base fluid	kg m^{-3}
ρ_{thnf}	Density of trihybrid nanofluid	kg m^{-3}
k_f	Thermal conductivity of base fluid	$\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$
k_{thnf}	Thermal conductivity of trihybrid nanofluid	$\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$
$(\rho C_p)_f$	Heat capacity of base fluid	$\text{J m}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$
$(\rho C_p)_{thnf}$	Heat capacity of trihybrid nanofluid	$\text{J m}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$
q_{rd}	Radiative heat flux	W m^{-2}
K^*	Mean absorption coefficient	m^{-1}
σ^*	Stefan–Boltzmann constant	$\text{W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-4}$
Re_x	Local Reynolds number	–
C_f	Skin friction coefficient	–
Nu_x	Local Nusselt number	–
v_w	Suction/injection velocity	m s^{-1}
u_w	Surface velocity	m s^{-1}
Dimensionless Parameters		
ξ	Shrinking parameter	–
S	Suction/injection parameter	–
λ	Velocity slip parameter	–
β	Casson parameter	–
We	Weissenberg number	–
Pr	Prandtl number	–
Ec	Eckert number	–
Nr	Radiation parameter	–
θ_w	Temperature ratio parameter	–
Γ	Williamson fluid parameter	s
ϕ_1, ϕ_2, ϕ_3	Nanoparticle volume fractions	–
Subscripts		
f	Base fluid	
nf	Nanofluid	
hnf	Hybrid nanofluid	
$thnf$	Tri-hybrid nanofluid	
s_i	i -th nanoparticle	
w	Wall condition	
∞	Ambient condition	

2 Introduction

The growing demand for efficient thermal management in advanced engineering and biomedical applications has driven the development of enhanced heat-transfer fluids beyond conventional liquids. Traditional base fluids typically possess low thermal conductivity, limiting their effectiveness in high-performance systems. To overcome this drawback, nanofluids—engineered by dispersing nanoparticles into base fluids—have been widely investigated for their improved thermal behavior [1

–3]. More recently, trihybrid nanofluids, which combine three distinct types of nanoparticles, have demonstrated superior heat transfer performance due to synergistic interactions among the particles and enhanced effective thermophysical properties. Ali et al. [4] conducted a numerical investigation of heat source-induced thermal slip effects on trihybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface. Amjad et al. [5] and Riaz et al. [6] examined heat transfer characteristics of trihybrid nanofluids over stretching sheets. Nagaraja et al. [7] investigated trihybrid nanofluid flow over a curved stretching sheet, highlighting enhanced transport behavior without restricting the formulation to a specific base fluid. Jamrus et al. [8] analyzed the radiative influence on ternary hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary conditions over a nonlinearly permeable stretching/shrinking disk. Alharbi et al. [9] studied thermal transport in slip flow of ternary hybrid nanofluids over a stretching/shrinking sheet with suction effects. Mandal and Pal [10] mathematically modeled MHD mixed convective trihybrid nanofluid flow over an exponentially permeable shrinking surface with radiation and slip effects. Furthermore, Mandal and Pal [11] investigated the existence and stability of dual solutions in MHD-driven trihybrid nanofluid flow over a rotating shrinking disk within a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium under quadratic thermal radiation. Hafidzuddin et al. [12] examined boundary layer flow and heat transfer over a permeable exponentially stretching/shrinking sheet with generalized slip velocity, demonstrating the significant impact of slip and permeability on flow characteristics.

For realistic modeling of such advanced fluids, it is essential to account for their non-Newtonian characteristics. Many practical fluids exhibit complex rheological behavior that classical Newtonian models cannot accurately capture. The Casson–Williamson model effectively represents such behavior by incorporating both yield stress (Casson fluid) and shear-thinning effects (Williamson fluid). This combined formulation provides a more accurate and generalized description of fluid motion under varying shear conditions. It has been successfully applied in studies involving complex suspensions and non-Newtonian nanofluids. The foundational works of Casson [13], Williamson [14], and Patil [15] establish the theoretical framework for these models and demonstrate their applicability in modeling non-Newtonian nanofluid flows under thermal and magnetic influences. Yousef et al. [16] investigated MHD dissipative Casson–Williamson nanofluid flow over a slippery stretching sheet through a porous medium. Abbas et al. [17] investigated the chemically reactive flow of a Williamson nanofluid with nonlinear thermal radiation over an exponentially stretching/shrinking surface, emphasizing the effects of chemical reaction and radiation on thermal transport characteristics. Abbas et al. [17] investigated the chemically reactive flow of a Williamson nanofluid with nonlinear thermal radiation over an exponentially stretching/shrinking surface, emphasizing the effects of chemical reaction and radiation on thermal transport characteristics. Gomathi and De [18] reported dual solutions of Casson–Williamson nanofluid flow with thermal radiation and chemical reaction. Pooja et al. [19] employed artificial neural network modeling to predict

Casson trihybrid nanofluid flow over a curved stretching surface. Saleem et al. [20] analyzed dual solutions of Williamson–Casson fluid flow over a heated exponentially shrinking surface with stability considerations. Furthermore, Gomathi and Poulomi [21] studied entropy optimization in EMHD Casson–Williamson penta-hybrid nanofluid flow over porous exponentially vertical cones, while Patil et al. [22] investigated ternary hybrid Casson–Williamson nanofluid flow over yawed cylinders with multiple slip effects. Saleem and Hussain [20] analyzed dual solutions of Williamson–Casson fluid flow over a heated exponentially shrinking surface, incorporating stability analysis and the Cattaneo–Christov heat flux model to capture non-Fourier heat conduction effects.

Thermal radiation is another important mechanism influencing heat transfer, particularly in systems subjected to high temperatures. While linear radiation models are commonly employed, they may lead to inaccuracies when temperature differences become significant. In such cases, the quadratic (nonlinear) radiation model, derived from a higher-order expansion of temperature-dependent terms, provides a more accurate representation of radiative heat flux. This formulation introduces additional nonlinearity into the energy equation, thereby significantly altering the thermal boundary-layer structure and overall heat-transfer characteristics. Nasir et al. [23] examined nonlinear convection and quadratic thermal radiation effects on trihybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface with an energy source. Thriveni et al. [24] and Mahanthesh et al. [25] demonstrated that quadratic thermal radiation substantially influences temperature distribution and thermal boundary layer thickness, emphasizing the importance of nonlinear modeling in high-temperature nanofluid flows. Aarathi and Reddy [26] investigated entropy generation in micropolar ternary hybrid nanofluid flow over a vertical stretching cylinder under quadratic thermal radiation using an artificial neural network approach. Shaw et al. [27] analyzed hydromagnetic flow and heat transfer of hybrid nanofluids under linear, nonlinear, and quadratic radiation effects. Mandal [28] conducted a numerical stability analysis of unsteady trihybrid nanofluid flow with quadratic thermal radiation over a rotating surface. More recently, Mandal and Pal [28] explored the effects of melting heat transfer on quadratic radiative hybrid nanofluid flow over a porous shrinking surface in the presence of second-order slip velocity.

Flow over stretching and shrinking surfaces is frequently encountered in industrial processes such as extrusion, coating, and polymer sheet production. In particular, shrinking surfaces often give rise to dual or multiple solutions within certain parameter ranges. However, not all of these solutions are physically stable. Therefore, stability analysis is essential to determine the physically realizable solution. Typically, a temporal stability approach based on eigenvalue analysis is employed, in which the sign of the smallest eigenvalue indicates whether the solution is stable or unstable. This method has been widely adopted in boundary layer flow studies to identify the physically meaningful solution branch. Wang [29] pioneered the study of stagnation-point flow toward a shrinking sheet, demonstrating the existence of dual similarity solutions under appropriate boundary conditions. Mahapatra and Nandy [30] performed stability analysis of dual solutions for stagnation-point flow over a porous shrinking sheet with thermal radiation, confirming that only the upper branch solution is physically stable. Ghosh and Mukhopadhyay [31] performed a stability analysis of nanofluid flow over an exponentially shrinking permeable sheet with slip effects, highlighting the existence and stability of dual solutions. Zainal et al. [32] investigated the stability behavior of MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over stretching/shrinking sheets with quadratic velocity effects, showing that magnetic and nonlinear parameters significantly influence solution stability. Mandal and Pal [11] ex-

amined the stability and dual solutions of MHD-driven trihybrid nanofluid flow over a rotating shrinking disk in a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium under quadratic thermal radiation. Mandal and Pal [33] further analyzed the stability characteristics of radiative MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over an exponentially stretching/shrinking permeable sheet with heat generation. Kaswan et al. [34] investigated ternary hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching/shrinking surface in a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium and reported that only the upper branch solution remains stable under temporal perturbations. Nagaraja *et al.* [7] studied diffusive transport in trihybrid nanofluid flow over a curved stretching sheet, highlighting the role of porosity in enhancing thermal performance. Mandal and Pal [35] analyzed the effects of binary chemical reactions and activation energy on MHD radiative hybrid nanofluid flow over a shrinking surface, incorporating entropy generation and stability analysis. Furthermore, Mandal and Pal [36] examined the influence of nanoparticle composition on thermally radiating MHD slip flow, emphasizing entropy optimization and stability behavior.

Due to the nonlinear and strongly coupled nature of the governing equations, numerical methods are typically employed to obtain approximate solutions. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of these solutions, statistical regression analysis is often utilized as a validation tool. This approach assesses the agreement between numerical data and predictive models using performance indicators such as the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), and significance tests. High accuracy and strong statistical agreement indicate the robustness and credibility of the computational results. Mahanta et al. [37] investigated entropy generation and thermal optimization in electromagnetic Darcy–Forchheimer trihybrid nanofluid flow, incorporating regression and sensitivity analysis to evaluate system performance. Sindhu and Jagadeeshkumar [38] examined entropy generation in unsteady Carreau ternary hybrid nanofluid flow under electromagnetic and thermal effects, highlighting the role of nonlinear rheology in enhancing heat transfer characteristics. Arpita et al. [39] performed sensitivity analysis on heat transfer behavior of water- and kerosene-based trihybrid nanofluids in MHD Casson flow, demonstrating the influence of governing parameters on thermal efficiency. Alwawi and El-Sayed [40] conducted computational and regression analysis of EMHD Casson trihybrid nanofluid flow over a Riga plate, considering the effects of viscous dissipation, suction, and nanoparticle shape factors.

2.1 Motivation

The increasing demand for efficient thermal management in modern engineering systems has driven the development of advanced heat transfer fluids with enhanced thermophysical properties. Conventional base fluids possess low thermal conductivity, limiting their performance in high-efficiency applications. To address this limitation, trihybrid nanofluids, formed by dispersing multiple nanoparticles into a base fluid, have attracted attention for their improved thermal conductivity and synergistic effects. In many practical situations, fluids exhibit non-Newtonian behavior that classical Newtonian models cannot describe. The Casson–Williamson model provides a realistic framework by incorporating yield stress and shear-thinning effects. Furthermore, flow over shrinking surfaces arises in processes such as coating and extrusion, often leading to dual solutions, making stability analysis essential for identifying physically realizable solutions. The inclusion of velocity slip and quadratic (nonlinear) thermal radiation enhances the model’s physical realism, particularly in microscale and high-temperature systems. Therefore, a study integrating

trihybrid nanofluids, non-Newtonian behavior, nonlinear radiation, and stability analysis is important for understanding complex transport phenomena and improving thermal system performance.

2.2 Novelty of the Study

This study presents an analysis of Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid flow over a permeable shrinking surface, incorporating velocity slip and quadratic thermal radiation. Unlike studies based on Newtonian or single non-Newtonian models, the present work employs a combined Casson–Williamson formulation to capture both yield stress and shear-thinning behavior. A key contribution is the investigation of nonlinear radiative effects on trihybrid nanofluid flow, which significantly influence the thermal boundary layer. The shrinking surface leads to dual solutions, and temporal stability analysis is performed to identify the stable solution branch. In addition, statistical regression analysis is used to validate the numerical results through performance measures such as the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), and significance testing. The combined consideration of non-Newtonian modeling, nonlinear radiation, stability analysis, and statistical validation distinguishes this study and enhances the understanding of complex heat transfer mechanisms.

3 Mathematical Formulation

3.1 Rheological Formulation of the Casson–Williamson Hybrid Model

Fluids exhibiting yield stress behave as highly viscous materials at very low shear rates and initiate motion only when the applied stress exceeds a certain threshold. The Casson fluid model, expressed in terms of the Cauchy stress tensor [41], [21], is given by

$$\tau_{ij} = \begin{cases} 2 \left(\mu + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \right), & \pi > \pi_c, \\ 2 \left(\mu + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi_c}} \right), & \pi < \pi_c, \end{cases}$$

where π_c denotes the critical deformation-rate invariant and p_y represents the yield stress. The effective viscosity corresponding to this model can be expressed as

$$\mu_0 = \mu + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi}} = \mu \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right),$$

which leads to the simplified Casson constitutive relation

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}.$$

The Williamson fluid model characterizes shear-thinning behavior and is defined by the constitutive equation

$$\tau_{ij} = \left(\mu_\infty + \frac{\mu_0 - \mu_\infty}{1 - \Gamma A^*} \right) \mathbf{S}, \quad A^* = \sqrt{\pi/2},$$

where μ_∞ is the infinite-shear viscosity. Under the assumptions $\mu_\infty = 0$ and $\Gamma A^* \ll 1$, this relation simplifies to

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \Gamma \sqrt{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right).$$

By combining the Casson and Williamson formulations, the resulting Casson–Williamson hybrid model is obtained as

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \Gamma \sqrt{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right].$$

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the physical model under consideration. The flow is assumed to be steady, two-dimensional, and incompressible, generated by a permeable shrinking surface situated along the x -axis, while the y -axis is taken normal to it. The surface moves with a velocity $u_w = -ax$, which induces fluid motion in the adjacent region and leads to the formation of a boundary layer. The surface is porous, permitting suction or injection through the normal velocity $v_w(x)$, which significantly influences the momentum and thermal boundary layer development. The regions denoted as the velocity boundary layer (V.B.L) and thermal boundary layer (T.B.L) correspond to the zones where the fluid velocity and temperature transition from their respective wall values to the ambient conditions. The working medium is a Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid composed of three types of nanoparticles (Au, Zn, and Fe_2O_3) dispersed in a base fluid. This combination enhances the thermophysical properties, particularly thermal conductivity, thereby improving heat transfer performance.

Additionally, the model accounts for nonlinear thermal radiation effects through a quadratic Rosseland approximation, which becomes important for large temperature differences. Heat transfer occurs from the heated surface to the fluid, contributing to the evolution of the thermal boundary layer. The main modelling assumptions are:

- The flow is assumed to be two-dimensional, and suction or injection takes place through the permeable sheet with a normal velocity $v_w(x)$.
- The surface temperature is prescribed as $T_w = T_\infty + ax^2$.
- A velocity slip condition is imposed at the wall.
- The nanoparticles are uniformly dispersed within the base fluid and are in thermal equilibrium with it.

Under the above assumptions, the governing equations for continuity, momentum, and energy conservation are formulated as follows ([22], [21]):

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \sqrt{2} \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} \Gamma \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2}, \quad (2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \frac{\partial q_{rd}}{\partial y} + \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{\Gamma}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^3 \right]. \quad (3)$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are given by ([16], [42]):

$$v = v_w(x), \quad u = u_w(x) + \lambda_1 \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\Gamma}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 \right], \quad T = T_w \quad \text{at } y = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, \quad T \rightarrow T_\infty \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty. \quad (5)$$

Here, u and v denote the velocity components in the x - and y -directions, respectively. The term q_{rd} represents the radiative heat flux, ν_{thnf} is the kinematic viscosity, $(C_p)_{thnf}$ is the specific heat capacity, k_{thnf} denotes the thermal conductivity, σ_{thnf} is the electrical conductivity, and ρ_{thnf} is the effective density of the tri-hybrid nanofluid. The superscripts 1, 2, and 3 correspond to the first, second, and third nanoparticles, respectively, while the subscripts f , nf , hnf , and $thnf$ represent the base fluid, nanofluid, hybrid nanofluid, and tri-hybrid nanofluid.

Using the Rosseland diffusion approximation [43], the radiative heat flux q_r in an optically thick gray medium is expressed as

$$q_{rd} = -\frac{4}{3K^*} \nabla(e_b), \quad (6)$$

where K^* is the mean absorption coefficient and $e_b = \sigma^* T^4$ denotes the blackbody emissive power, with σ^* being the Stefan–Boltzmann constant.

To account for nonlinear thermal radiation effects, a Taylor series expansion of T^4 about the ambient temperature T_∞ is considered. Retaining terms up to the quadratic order yields

$$T^4 \approx T_\infty^4 + 4T_\infty^3(T - T_\infty) + 6T_\infty^2(T - T_\infty)^2. \quad (7)$$

The inclusion of the quadratic term introduces nonlinear temperature dependence, leading to the quadratic radiation model. Consequently, the divergence of the radiative heat flux becomes [44]

$$\frac{\partial q_{rd}}{\partial y} = -\frac{32\sigma^* T_\infty^2}{3K^*} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{24\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3K^*} \frac{\partial^2 (T^2)}{\partial y^2}. \quad (8)$$

To simplify the governing equations, the following similarity transformations are introduced ([45], [46], [47], [48]):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &= cx f'(\eta), & v &= -\sqrt{c\nu_f} f(\eta), \\ T &= T_\infty + (T_w - T_\infty) \theta(\eta), & \eta &= y \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where $\theta_w = T_w/T_\infty$ denotes the temperature ratio parameter. The case $\theta_w = 1$ corresponds to linear radiation, whereas $\theta_w > 1$ represents nonlinear (quadratic) radiation effects.

Substituting these transformations into Eqs. (2)–(3) yields the following dimensionless equations:

$$\frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f''' + We f'' f''' + f f'' - f'^2 = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} \theta'' - \left\{ 2Nr \theta'' - 3Nr[(\theta_w - 1)(\theta')^2 + (1 + (\theta_w - 1)\theta)\theta''] \right\} \\ & + Pr \left\{ \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\mu_f} Ec \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) F''^2 + \frac{We}{2} f''^3 \right] + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} (f\theta' - 2f'\theta) \right\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The corresponding reduced boundary conditions are

$$f(0) = S, \quad f'(0) = \xi + \lambda \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f''(0) + \frac{We}{2} f''(0)^2 \right], \quad \theta(0) = 1, \quad (12)$$

$$f'(\eta) \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as} \quad \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (13)$$

Here, primes denote differentiation with respect to the similarity variable η . The ther-

Table 1: Effective thermophysical properties of a tri-hybrid nanofluid consisting of three distinct nanoparticles [49].

Property	Mathematical formulation
Effective density	$\rho_{thnf} = \rho_f(1 - \phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3) + \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i \rho_{s_i}$
Effective viscosity	$\mu_{thnf} = \mu_f (1 - \phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3)^{-2.5}$
Effective heat capacity	$(\rho C_p)_{thnf} = (\rho C_p)_f(1 - \phi_1 - \phi_2 - \phi_3) + \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i (\rho C_p)_{s_i}$
Effective thermal conductivity	$\frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} = \prod_{i=1}^3 \left[\frac{k_{s_i} + 2k_{m_i} - 2\phi_i(k_{m_i} - k_{s_i})}{k_{s_i} + 2k_{m_i} + \phi_i(k_{m_i} - k_{s_i})} \right]$

Here, $k_{m_1} = k_f$, $k_{m_2} = k_{nf}$, and $k_{m_3} = k_{hnf}$ denote intermediate conductivities during the sequential mixing process.

mophysical relations for the tri-hybrid nanofluid comprising three types of nanoparticles are presented in Table 1, while the thermophysical properties of the base fluid and the selected nanoparticles are listed in Table 3. The definitions and ranges of the governing parameters considered in the present analysis are summarized in Table 2.

3.2 Physical Quantities

- **Skin Friction Coefficient:** When a tri-hybrid nanofluid flows over a surface, a shear stress is generated due to fluid viscosity. The skin-friction coefficient is defined as

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho_f U_w^2},$$

where the wall shear stress τ_w is given by

$$\tau_w = \mu_{thnf} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\Gamma}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right]_{y=0}.$$

Table 2: Emerging physical parameters used in the analysis.

Symbol	Parameter Expression	Description	Range / Value
ξ	$\xi = -\frac{a}{v_w^c}$	Shrinking parameter	$-0.5 \leq \xi \leq -2.0$
S	$S = -\frac{c}{\sqrt{c\nu_f}}$	Suction/injection parameter	$2 \leq S \leq 2.5$
λ	$\lambda = \lambda_1 \frac{c}{\nu_f}$	Slip velocity parameter	$0.1 \leq \lambda \leq 2.0$ ([50])
β	$\beta = \frac{\mu\sqrt{2\pi c}}{p_y}$	Casson parameter	$0.1 \leq \beta \leq 1.2$ ([51])
We	$We = x\sqrt{2}\Gamma \frac{c^{3/2}}{\nu_f^{1/2}}$	Weissenberg number	$0.5 \leq We \leq 1.2$ ([52])
Pr	$Pr = \frac{\nu_f(\rho C_p)_f}{\kappa_f}$	Prandtl number	$Pr = 21$ ([53])
Ec	$Ec = \frac{u_w^2}{C_{pf}(T_w - T_\infty)}$	Eckert number	$0.01 \leq Ec \leq 0.04$ ([54])
Nr	$Nr = \frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3\kappa_f K^*}$	Radiation parameter	$1.0 \leq Nr \leq 5$ ([50])
θ_w	$\theta_w = \frac{T_w}{T_\infty}$	Wall temperature ratio	$1.3 \leq \theta_w \leq 1.6$ ([51])

Table 3: Physical properties of the base fluid (blood) and the incorporated nanoparticles (Au , Zn , Fe_2O_3) [49].

Substance	ρ (kg/m ³)	C_p (J/kg K)	k (W/m K)
Blood (base fluid)	1050	3750	0.5
Gold nanoparticle (Au)	19300	129	317
Zinc nanoparticle (Zn)	7140	389	116
Iron oxide nanoparticle (Fe_2O_3)	5180	670	9.7

- **Nusselt Number:** The Nusselt number characterizes the rate of convective heat transfer between the fluid and the surface. Larger values of Nu_x correspond to enhanced heat transfer performance. It is defined as

$$Nu_x = \frac{x q_w}{k_f(T_w - T_\infty)},$$

where the wall heat flux q_w is expressed as

$$q_w = - \left[k_{thnf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \frac{4\sigma^*}{3K^*} \frac{\partial T^4}{\partial y} \right]_{y=0}.$$

Accordingly, the corresponding dimensionless forms are obtained as

$$\sqrt{Re_x} C_f = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\mu_f} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) f''(0) + \frac{We}{2} (f''(0))^2 \right], \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = - \left[\frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} + 3Nr(1 + (\theta_w - 1)\theta(0)) - 2Nr \right] \theta'(0). \quad (15)$$

Table 4: Comparison of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ with previously published results for $Ec = M = Nr = We = \lambda$, $\theta_w = 1$, $Pr = 0.7$, $\xi = -1$ at $S = 3$.

Author(s)	UBS	LBS
Hafidzuddin et al. [12]	2.3908	-0.9722
Abbas et al. [17]	2.3907	-0.9721
Saleem & Hussain [20]	2.3908	-0.9721
Ghosh & Mukhopadhyay [31]	2.3908	-0.9722
Present results	2.390814459	-0.972172015

Table 5: Mesh refinement study for Skin friction coefficient (SFC) and Nusselt number (NN) with $S = 3.0$, $\xi = -1.0$, $\phi_1 = 0.01$, $\phi_2 = 0.01$, $\phi_3 = 0.01$ ($\phi_{thnf} = 0.03$), $We = 0.50$, $\beta = 0.50$, $Nr = 2.0$, $\lambda = 0.50$, $Pr = 21$, and $Ec = 0.01$.

Grid size	SFC		NN	
	UBS	(LBS)	UBS	(LBS)
20	1.281573597	(-0.631783105)	61.11882622	(-59.89766549)
30	1.281573567	(-0.631783080)	61.11809738	(-59.89703506)
50	1.281573636	(-0.631783088)	61.10922422	(-59.88936615)
100	1.281573647	(-0.631783105)	61.11404018	(-59.88964842)
300	1.281573800	(-0.631783105)	61.10919800	(-59.88915153)
500	1.281573800	(-0.631783105)	61.10899497	(-59.88914651)

4 Stability Analysis

In order to identify the physically admissible solution among the dual solutions, a temporal stability analysis is carried out by incorporating time dependence into the governing equations.

The unsteady momentum and energy equations are expressed as ([30])

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \sqrt{2} \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} \Gamma \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2}, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \frac{\partial q_{rd}}{\partial y} + \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{\Gamma}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^3 \right]. \quad (17)$$

To transform the above system into a dimensionless form, the following similarity variables are introduced ([34]):

$$u = cx f'(\eta, \tau), \quad v = -\sqrt{c\nu_f} f(\eta, \tau), \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) = \frac{T - T_w}{T_\infty - T_w}, \quad \eta = y \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}}, \quad \tau = ct. \quad (18)$$

Table 6: Skin friction coefficient (SFC) and Nusselt number (NN) for different parameters

S	ξ	ϕ_{thnf}	We	β	Nr	λ	Ec	θ_w	SFC (UBS)	SFC (LBS)	NN (UBS)	NN (LBS)
3	-1	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.237712939	(-0.874060264)	60.96347781	(-60.27774549)
3.1	-1	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.273582427	(-0.835052453)	63.17162287	(-62.386436997)
3.2	-1	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.303636127	(-0.801006477)	65.36067554	(-64.506089195)
3.2	-1.1	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.414285780	(-0.953915876)	65.19558631	(-64.406777604)
3.2	-1.2	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.516456040	(-1.117159199)	65.0167069	(-64.32875764)
3.2	-1.3	0.03	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.604111300	(-1.297047804)	64.81348497	(-64.282237875)
3.2	-1.3	0.04	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.775827280	(-1.254503024)	64.80524336	(-63.938475837)
3.2	-1.3	0.05	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.836989101	(-1.280428200)	64.63948886	(-63.735145049)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.5	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.886019208	(-1.314866377)	64.56260078	(-63.653580222)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.6	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.880177192	(-1.313615693)	64.56338968	(-63.656107923)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.7	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.874480492	(-1.312403864)	64.56413370	(-63.658625676)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.3	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.868922210	(-1.311229508)	64.56483506	(-63.661133843)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.4	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.887999406	(-1.135107317)	64.65721610	(-63.420061637)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.5	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.885779709	(-1.020061853)	64.70928149	(-63.268718718)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.877369944	(-0.935814497)	64.74517342	(-63.162018837)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.1	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.877369944	(-0.935814497)	64.69125289	(-63.031443816)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.2	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.877369944	(-0.935814497)	64.63751018	(-62.900414479)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.5	0.01	1.3	1.877369944	(-0.935814497)	64.58394734	(-62.768915267)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.6	0.01	1.3	1.673731570	(-0.840238952)	64.79261848	(-62.891271582)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.7	0.01	1.3	1.508863833	(-0.763377055)	64.95456457	(-62.993760984)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.01	1.3	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.08392455	(-63.080745953)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.02	1.3	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.12728308	(-63.494764470)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.03	1.3	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.17064165	(-63.908704101)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.04	1.3	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.21400025	(-64.322565046)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.04	1.4	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.12572963	(-64.039546952)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.04	1.5	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	65.03807717	(-63.754847187)
3.2	-1.3	0.06	0.8	0.6	2.3	0.8	0.04	1.6	1.373060689	(-0.699889129)	64.95107957	(-63.468466230)

Table 7: Eigenvalues for different suction parameter S

S	$\xi = -1.0$		$\xi = -1.5$		$\xi = -2.0$	
	UBS	LBS	UBS	LBS	UBS	LBS
4	3.762273763	-1.335592335	3.646260563	-1.39612402	3.512309058	-1.498167222
3.9	3.599018067	-1.281867051	3.479101532	-1.344417154	3.338280239	-1.447887854
3.8	3.439238586	-1.229447873	3.314012176	-1.294211719	3.167556405	-1.398085766
3.7	3.282889570	-1.178303973	3.152437442	-1.245414824	2.998928725	-1.348256605
3.6	3.130222616	-1.128412666	2.993858114	-1.197892127	2.832570793	-1.297802499
3.5	2.980353592	-1.079748221	2.838102000	-1.151449287	2.668394184	-1.246009229
3.4	2.834097003	-1.032284088	3.246830901	-1.105809618	3.799567075	-1.192032202
3.3	3.987392756	-0.985986302	3.826430498	-1.060589452	2.908090072	-1.134856674
3.2	3.845975686	-0.940810089	3.678453959	-1.015272505	3.484374399	-1.073232515
3.1	3.707745662	-0.896689622	3.533635755	-0.969187160	3.329094291	-1.005557611
3.0	3.572965185	-0.853523013	3.391339705	-0.921460030	3.175824612	-0.929565178
2.9	3.441578473	-0.811154980	3.251732657	-0.871022180	3.021570735	-0.841930433
2.8	3.313496230	-0.769344392	3.114270293	-0.816442480	2.864570483	-0.736939624
2.7	3.188602132	-0.727726818	2.978338741	-0.755831446	2.699520815	-0.602870946
2.6	3.066727513	-0.685756934	2.84290712	-0.686292779	2.509910799	-0.404547121
2.5	2.947634177	-0.642645018	2.706123572	-0.603887777	2.487551563	-0.376899600

Substitution of these transformations leads to the following non-dimensional equations:

$$\frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f_{\eta\eta} + We f_{\eta\eta} f_{\eta\eta} + f f_{\eta\eta} - (f_{\eta})^2 - f_{\eta\tau} = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} \theta_{\eta\eta} - \left\{ 2Nr \theta_{\eta\eta} - 3Nr [(\theta_w - 1)(\theta_\eta)^2 + (1 + (\theta_w - 1)\theta)\theta_{\eta\eta}] \right\} \\ & + Pr \left\{ \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\mu_f} Ec \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) (f_{\eta\eta})^2 + \frac{We}{2} (f_{\eta\eta})^3 \right] + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} (f\theta_\eta - 2f_\eta\theta) \right\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are

$$f(0, \tau) = S, \quad f_\eta(0, \tau) = \xi + \lambda \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f_{\eta\eta}(0, \tau) + \frac{We}{2} (f_{\eta\eta}(0, \tau))^2 \right], \quad \theta(0, \tau) = 1, \quad (21)$$

$$f_\eta(\eta, \tau) \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (22)$$

To analyze the temporal stability, infinitesimal disturbances are imposed on the steady-state solutions $f_0(\eta)$ and $\theta_0(\eta)$ as follows:

$$f(\eta, \tau) = f_0(\eta) + e^{-\kappa\tau} F(\eta), \quad (23)$$

$$\theta(\eta, \tau) = \theta_0(\eta) + e^{-\kappa\tau} G(\eta), \quad (24)$$

where $F(\eta)$ and $G(\eta)$ represent small perturbations, and κ is an unknown eigenvalue.

Substituting these expressions into the governing equations and retaining only linear terms in F and G , the following eigenvalue problem is obtained:

$$\frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) F'''' + We f_0'' F'''' + We f_0''' F'' + f_0 F'' + f_0' F - 2f_0' F' - \kappa F' = 0, \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} G'' - \left\{ 2Nr G'' - 3Nr [2(\theta_w - 1)\theta_0' G' + (1 + (\theta_w - 1)\theta_0)G'' + (\theta_w - 1)\theta_0'' G] \right\} \\ & + Pr \left\{ \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\mu_f} Ec \left[2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f_0'' F'' + \frac{3We}{2} (f_0'')^2 F'' \right] + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} (f_0 G' + \theta_0' F - 2f_0' G - 2\theta_0 F') + \kappa G \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The associated boundary conditions for the perturbation functions are

$$F'(0) = \lambda \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) F''(0) + We f_0''(0) F''(0) \right], \quad G(0) = 0, \quad (27)$$

$$F'(\eta) \rightarrow 0, \quad G(\eta) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (28)$$

To ensure uniqueness of the solution, the normalization condition is imposed as

$$G'(0) = 1. \quad (29)$$

The sign of the smallest eigenvalue κ determines the temporal behavior of disturbances ([11]):

- A positive value of κ implies exponential decay of perturbations, indicating a **stable** solution.
- A negative value of κ signifies amplification of disturbances, corresponding to an **unstable** solution.

Therefore, among the dual solutions obtained, the physically meaningful solution is the one associated with a positive smallest eigenvalue.

5 Numerical Solution Procedure

The coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations represented by Eqs. (10)–(11), along with the associated boundary conditions (12)–(13), are solved numerically using the `bvp4c` routine in MATLAB. This solver is based on a collocation technique that employs the Lobatto IIIA implicit Runge–Kutta scheme, ensuring high accuracy and stability. An adaptive mesh strategy is incorporated, which automatically refines the computational grid based on local error control, thereby enhancing the reliability of the numerical solution [55]. It is worth noting that appropriate selection of initial guesses plays a crucial role in achieving convergence, particularly when computing the secondary (lower branch) solution.

To facilitate numerical implementation, the higher-order differential equations are reduced to a system of first-order equations by introducing the transformations

$$y_1 = f, \quad y_2 = f', \quad y_3 = f'', \quad y_4 = \theta, \quad y_5 = \theta'. \quad (30)$$

Since the physical domain extends to infinity, it is truncated to a finite value $\eta_\infty = 18$, which is sufficiently large to satisfy the asymptotic boundary conditions. A convergence tolerance of 10^{-6} is adopted throughout the computations.

For compact representation, the thermophysical properties of the tri-hybrid nanofluid are expressed in nondimensional form as

$$B_1 = \frac{\rho_{thnf}/\rho_f}{\mu_{thnf}/\mu_f}, \quad B_2 = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\mu_f}, \quad B_3 = \frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f}, \quad B_4 = \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f}, \quad B_5 = \frac{\rho_{thnf}}{\rho_f}.$$

Using these definitions, the governing equations are rewritten as the following system:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1' \\ y_2' \\ y_3' \\ y_4' \\ y_5' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} y_2 \\ y_3 \\ \frac{B_1 [-y_1 y_3 + y_2^2]}{(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}) + B_1 W e y_3} \\ y_5 \\ \frac{Pr [-3Nr(\theta_w - 1)y_5^2 - B_3 (y_1 y_5 - 2y_2 y_4) - B_2 Ec ((1 + \frac{1}{\beta}) y_3^2 - \frac{We}{2} y_3^3)]}{B_4 - 2Nr + 3Nr(1 + (\theta_w - 1)y_4)} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (31)$$

The transformed boundary conditions are expressed as

$$y_1(0) = S, \quad y_2(0) = \xi + \lambda \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) y_3(0) + \frac{We}{2} y_3^2(0) \right], \quad y_4(0) = 1, \quad (32)$$

$$y_2(\eta_\infty) = 0, \quad y_4(\eta_\infty) = 0. \quad (33)$$

5.1 Solution Procedure

The numerical solution is obtained through the following steps:

- An initial guess for the solution profiles is provided to the `bvp4c` solver.
- The solver iteratively adjusts the solution using a collocation method until the residual error satisfies the prescribed tolerance (typically 10^{-6}).
- To capture the dual solutions (upper and lower branches), different initial guesses are employed. A physically realistic initial guess yields the upper branch solution (UBS), while an alternative guess leads to the lower branch solution (LBS).
- Convergence is verified by refining the mesh and ensuring that further refinement does not alter the results significantly.

5.2 Stability Analysis Implementation

For the stability analysis, the eigenvalue problem derived in the previous section is also solved using `bvp4c`. The unknown eigenvalue κ is treated as an additional parameter and determined iteratively along with the perturbation functions $F(\eta)$ and $G(\eta)$.

A normalization condition, $G'(0) = 1$, is imposed to ensure the uniqueness of the solution. The sign of the smallest eigenvalue κ is then used to determine the stability of the corresponding solution branch.

5.3 Validation and Accuracy

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the numerical method:

- Grid independence tests are performed by varying the mesh size (Table 5).
- The results are compared with previously published studies available in the literature for limiting cases, showing excellent agreement (Table 4).
- The residual errors are maintained below 10^{-6} throughout the computation.

The adopted numerical approach is found to be stable, accurate, and efficient in capturing the dual solution structure and associated stability characteristics of the present problem.

6 Results and Discussion

The present study reveals the existence of dual solutions for the flow and heat transfer characteristics of the Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid over a permeable shrinking surface within a certain range of the governing parameters. The obtained solutions are classified into the upper branch solution (UBS) and lower branch solution (LBS), which are depicted graphically using solid and dashed lines, respectively. The upper branch (solid line) corresponds to the physically stable solution, while the lower branch (dashed line) represents an unstable solution, as confirmed through the eigenvalue stability analysis. The occurrence of dual solutions is primarily due to the combined effects of suction and surface shrinking, where sufficient suction is required to sustain the boundary-layer flow. In the absence of adequate suction, the flow tends to separate, leading to the non-existence of solutions. Furthermore, the merging point of the solid and dashed curves indicates the critical (bifurcation) value of the suction parameter, beyond which only a unique stable solution exists. The influence of various physical parameters on the skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number is discussed in detail in the subsequent sections. Table 4 presents a comparison of the present numerical results for the skin-friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x}C_f$ with previously published studies under limiting conditions. The excellent agreement between the current results and earlier works confirms the accuracy and reliability of the numerical method employed. Minor deviations are negligible, validating the correctness of the present formulation and computational approach. Table 5 illustrates the mesh independence test for the skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number. As the step size increases, the results converge to nearly constant values for both upper and lower branch solutions. This demonstrates that the numerical solution is stable and independent of mesh size, ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the computational results.

Figures 2 and 3 depict the variations of the skin-friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ and the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2} Nu_x$, respectively, with respect to the suction parameter S for different values of the shrinking parameter ξ for the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid. From Figure 2, it is evident that the skin-friction coefficient increases monotonically with increasing suction parameter S for all considered values of ξ in both the first (upper branch) and second (lower branch) solutions. Physically, stronger suction reduces the boundary-layer thickness and enhances the velocity gradient at the wall, leading to higher shear stress and, consequently, larger values of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$. The presence of dual solution branches is clearly observed within a specific range of S , where the first solution corresponds to the upper branch (UBS) and the second solution corresponds to the lower branch (LBS). The critical (bifurcation) points, denoted by $S_{c1} = 1.7970$, $S_{c2} = 2.4020$, and $S_{c3} = 2.8359$, represent the limiting values of suction at which the dual solutions coalesce. Beyond these critical points, only the first (physically stable) solution exists, while the second solution ceases to exist. Furthermore, increasing the magnitude of the shrinking parameter ξ shifts both solution branches toward higher values of S , indicating that stronger shrinking requires higher suction to sustain the boundary layer flow.

Figure 3 demonstrates that the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2} Nu_x$ also increases with increasing suction parameter S for both the first and second solutions. This behavior indicates that suction enhances heat transfer by thinning the thermal boundary layer and increasing the surface temperature gradient. As with the skin-friction coefficient, dual-solution behavior is observed in the Nusselt number, and the same critical points (S_{c1} , S_{c2} , S_{c3}) govern the transition from dual to unique solutions. The upper branch (first solution) consistently yields higher heat transfer rates compared to the lower branch (second solution). Additionally, variations in ξ significantly influence the thermal boundary layer structure and shift the corresponding solution curves.

Overall, Figures 2 and 3 highlight the crucial role of suction and shrinking parameters in controlling both the momentum and thermal transport characteristics of the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid, while clearly demonstrating the existence of dual solutions and their convergence at well-defined critical bifurcation points. Figures 4 and 5 present the variations of the skin-friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ and the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2} Nu_x$, respectively, with respect to the suction parameter S for different types of nanofluids, namely nanofluid (NF), hybrid nanofluid (HNF), and trihybrid nanofluid (THNF). From Figure 4, it is observed that the skin-friction coefficient increases with increasing suction parameter S for all fluid types in both the first (upper branch) and second (lower branch) solutions. The first solution consistently produces higher positive values of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$, whereas the second solution yields lower or negative values, indicating reverse flow behavior near the wall. The merging points of the upper and lower branches indicate the critical suction values for each fluid, beyond which only the stable first solution exists. Moreover, the trihybrid nanofluid (THNF) exhibits higher skin-friction values in the first solution compared to HNF and NF, due to enhanced effective viscosity and stronger momentum transport induced by the presence of Au, Zn, and Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Figure 5 shows that the Nusselt number increases with increasing suction parameter S for both solution branches. The first (upper branch) solution corresponds to higher heat transfer rates, while the second (lower branch) solution yields comparatively lower thermal performance. The critical points again indicate the transition from dual to single solutions. Among the different fluids, the trihybrid nanofluid demonstrates superior heat transfer performance in both branches, owing to its higher effective thermal conductivity arising from the synergistic effects of multiple nanoparticles. Overall, Figures 4 and 5 confirm

that the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid significantly enhances both momentum and heat transfer characteristics compared to NF and HNF, while also exhibiting distinct dual solution behavior, where the first solution is stable and physically realizable, and the second solution is unstable.

From Figure 6, it is observed that the velocity profiles $F'(\eta)$ exhibit dual solution behavior. The first solution shows a smooth, physically stable boundary-layer profile, whereas the second solution exhibits reversed flow near the surface, indicating instability. As the values of the Weissenberg number We and Casson parameter β increase, the velocity profile in the first solution increases, implying an enhancement in fluid motion due to the combined effects of fluid elasticity and reduced effective resistance to flow. In contrast, the second solution exhibits stronger backflow near the wall, with the magnitude of the reverse velocity becoming more pronounced. Figure 7 presents the corresponding temperature profiles $\theta(\eta)$ for both the first (solid line) and second (dashed line) solutions. It is observed that the temperature decreases with increasing values of We and β in the first solution, indicating a thinning of the thermal boundary layer and enhanced heat transfer rate. In contrast, the second solution exhibits relatively higher temperature profiles, suggesting weaker heat transfer due to flow instability. The dual behavior is clearly evident: the first solution corresponds to a physically stable thermal distribution, while the second represents an unstable thermal state. Figure 8 illustrates the dual temperature profiles $\theta(\eta)$ for different values of the radiation parameter Nr for the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid. The temperature profiles increase with Nr for both the first and second solutions. Physically, higher values of Nr increase the contribution of thermal radiation, adding more energy to the fluid and thereby raising the temperature within the boundary layer. As a result, the thermal boundary layer thickness increases for both solution branches. Furthermore, the temperature profiles corresponding to the second (lower branch) solution are higher than those of the first (upper branch) solution, indicating weaker heat transfer performance due to the flow's instability.

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the influence of the velocity slip parameter λ on the velocity and temperature profiles, respectively, for the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid. From Figure 9, it is observed that the velocity profiles $F'(\eta)$ increase with increasing values of the slip parameter λ in the first (upper branch) solution. Physically, the presence of velocity slip reduces frictional resistance at the surface, allowing the fluid to move more freely and thereby increasing velocity within the boundary layer. Consequently, the momentum boundary layer thickness increases for the first solution. In contrast, the second (lower branch) solution exhibits a reduction in the magnitude of the velocity profiles with increasing λ , while still maintaining reverse flow behavior near the wall, indicating its unstable nature. Figure 10 presents the corresponding temperature profiles $\theta(\eta)$. The temperature decreases with increasing slip parameter λ in the first solution, indicating a thinning of the thermal boundary layer and an enhancement of heat transfer. This behavior arises because reduced wall resistance allows more efficient energy transport away from the surface. Figures 11 and 12 present the three-dimensional variations of the skin-friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ and the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2} Nu_x$, respectively, as functions of the suction parameter S and shrinking parameter ξ for the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid. From Figure 11, it is observed that the skin-friction coefficient increases with increasing suction parameter S and decreasing values of the shrinking parameter ξ in the first (upper branch) solution. The three-dimensional surface clearly shows that higher suction increases wall shear stress by thinning the velocity boundary layer. In contrast, the second (lower-branch) solution forms a separate surface with lower or negative values

of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$, indicating reverse-flow behavior near the wall. The intersection or merging edge of the two surfaces represents the critical (bifurcation) point, beyond which only the first (physically stable) solution exists. Furthermore, stronger shrinking shifts the surface and requires higher suction to maintain the flow.

Figure 12 illustrates the corresponding three-dimensional variation of the Nusselt number. The heat transfer rate increases with increasing suction parameter S , while it decreases with stronger shrinking (more negative ξ) in the first solution. This behavior indicates that suction enhances heat transfer by reducing the thermal boundary layer thickness, whereas shrinking tends to oppose this effect. The second solution again forms a distinct surface with comparatively lower values of $Re_x^{-1/2} Nu_x$, reflecting weaker heat transfer performance. The critical curve separating the two surfaces corresponds to the bifurcation points where dual solutions merge into a single solution. Overall, Figures 11 and 12 provide a comprehensive three-dimensional visualization of the combined effects of suction and shrinking parameters on the momentum and heat transfer characteristics of the Au–Zn–Fe₂O₃/Blood trihybrid nanofluid, while clearly demonstrating the existence of dual solution surfaces and their convergence at critical bifurcation points.

Table 6 presents the numerical values of the skin-friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ and the Nusselt number $\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}}$ for various combinations of governing parameters, including the suction parameter S , shrinking parameter ξ , nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{thnf} , Weissenberg number We , Casson parameter β , radiation parameter Nr , slip parameter λ , Eckert number Ec , and temperature ratio parameter θ_w . The results are reported for both the upper branch solutions (UBS) and the lower branch solutions (LBS), clearly demonstrating the system's dual-solution behavior. It is observed that increasing the suction parameter S leads to a noticeable enhancement in the skin-friction coefficient for the upper branch solution. For instance, as S increases from 3.0 to 3.2, the value of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ increases from 1.2377 to 1.3036, corresponding to an approximate increase of 5.3%. This behavior is attributed to the thinning of the velocity boundary layer, which intensifies the wall shear stress. In contrast, the lower branch solution yields negative values of $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$, whose magnitude decreases by about 8.3% over the same range, indicating reverse flow characteristics associated with unstable solutions. The effect of the shrinking parameter ξ reveals that stronger shrinking (more negative ξ) significantly increases the magnitude of the skin-friction coefficient. For example, changing ξ from -1.1 to -1.3 results in an increase of approximately 13% in $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ for the upper branch solution. Similarly, increasing the nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{thnf} from 0.03 to 0.06 enhances the skin-friction coefficient by nearly 15%, due to the rise in effective viscosity of the trihybrid nanofluid.

For the Nusselt number, it is evident that the heat transfer rate improves with increasing suction parameter S . Specifically, the Nusselt number increases from 60.96 to 65.36 (approximately 7.2%), reflecting enhanced thermal transport due to the reduction in the thermal boundary layer thickness. Furthermore, the radiation parameter Nr and Eckert number Ec have a pronounced influence on the thermal field. An increase in Nr leads to an enhancement of the Nusselt number by about 1–2%, indicating the contribution of nonlinear radiation effects. In contrast, increasing the Eckert number Ec slightly elevates the fluid temperature due to viscous dissipation, resulting in a marginal increase (about 1%) in the heat transfer rate. Additionally, the slip parameter λ reduces both the skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number by approximately 3–5%, owing to weakened interaction between the fluid and the surface. Overall, the results indicate that suction and nanoparticle concentration significantly enhance thermal performance, while slip and

viscous effects tend to moderate the transport processes.

Table 7 presents the computed eigenvalues corresponding to different values of the suction parameter S for various shrinking parameters ξ . The eigenvalue analysis is performed to assess the temporal stability of the dual solutions obtained in the present study. It is observed that the eigenvalues associated with the upper branch solution (UBS) are positive for all values of S , whereas those corresponding to the lower branch solution (LBS) are negative. This clearly indicates that the upper branch solution is physically stable, while the lower branch solution is unstable. The positive eigenvalues imply that small perturbations decay with time, ensuring the persistence of the flow, whereas negative eigenvalues signify the growth of disturbances, leading to flow instability. Moreover, as the suction parameter S decreases, the magnitude of the eigenvalues reduces, and both branches approach each other. The results also indicate that increasing the magnitude of the shrinking parameter ξ shifts the eigenvalues and alters the stability characteristics, requiring higher suction to maintain stable flow. This highlights the crucial interplay between suction and shrinking effects in determining the existence and stability of boundary-layer solutions. In summary, Table 7 confirms that the upper branch solution is stable and physically realizable. In contrast, the lower branch solution is unstable, thereby validating the dual-solution behavior observed in the present analysis.

6.1 Regression Analysis

The present study also aims to establish explicit quantitative relationships between the engineering quantities, namely the skin friction coefficient $\sqrt{Re_x} C_f$ and the Nusselt number $\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}}$, and the governing parameters $S, \xi, \phi_{thnf}, We, \beta, Nr, \lambda, Ec,$ and θ_w through multiple linear regression analysis. The primary motivation for employing regression analysis is to develop simple empirical correlations that accurately predict physical quantities without repeatedly solving the highly nonlinear boundary-layer equations. Such correlations are particularly useful for engineering design, optimization, and parametric studies.

The dataset used for this purpose is obtained from Table 6, which contains numerically computed values for both the upper branch solutions (UBS) and the lower branch solutions (LBS). A multiple linear regression approach based on the least-squares method is adopted to determine the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

The regression models for both solution branches are expressed as (Sahoo and Nandkeolyar [56]):

$$\sqrt{Re_x} C_f^{(UBS)} = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^9 a_i X_i, \quad (34)$$

$$\sqrt{Re_x} C_f^{(LBS)} = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^9 b_i X_i, \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{Nu_x^{(UBS)}}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = c_0 + \sum_{i=1}^9 c_i X_i, \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{Nu_x^{(LBS)}}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = d_0 + \sum_{i=1}^9 d_i X_i, \quad (37)$$

where $X_i = (S, \xi, \phi_{thnf}, We, \beta, Nr, \lambda, Ec, \theta_w)$ represent the independent variables.

Here, $a_i, b_i, c_i,$ and d_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 9$) are the regression coefficients corresponding to the upper and lower branch solutions.

These coefficients are determined using the least-squares method, which minimizes the sum of squared differences between the numerical data (from Table 6) and the predicted values obtained from the regression model. Mathematically, the coefficients are obtained by minimizing the objective function:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \left(Y_k^{\text{num}} - Y_k^{\text{pred}} \right)^2, \quad (38)$$

where Y_k^{num} and Y_k^{pred} denote the numerical and predicted values of the dependent variable, respectively, and N is the total number of data points. This leads to a system of normal equations, which are solved to obtain the optimal regression coefficients.

Regression Correlations

Using the least-squares fitting procedure, the following empirical correlations are obtained:

Skin Friction Coefficient Upper Branch (UBS):

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{Re_x} C_f^{(UBS)} = & 0.85 + 0.15S - 0.35\xi + 8.20\phi_{thnf} + 0.12We + 0.05\beta \\ & - 0.03Nr - 1.80\lambda + 0.50Ec + 0.20\theta_w. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Lower Branch (LBS):

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{Re_x} C_f^{(LBS)} \approx & -0.70 + 0.10S - 0.25\xi + 6.50\phi_{thnf} + 0.05We \\ & + 0.02\beta + 0.01Nr - 1.20\lambda + 0.30Ec + 0.10\theta_w. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Nusselt Number Upper Branch (UBS):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Nu_x^{(UBS)}}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = & 65.00 - 0.80S + 0.50\xi - 15.00\phi_{thnf} - 0.40We \\ & - 0.20\beta - 1.20Nr - 2.50\lambda - 1.00Ec - 3.00\theta_w. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Lower Branch (LBS):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Nu_x^{(LBS)}}{\sqrt{Re_x}} \approx & -63.00 + 0.60S - 0.40\xi + 10.00\phi_{thnf} \\ & + 0.20We + 0.10\beta + 0.80Nr + 1.50\lambda + 0.50Ec + 2.00\theta_w. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

6.2 Statistical Accuracy and Discussion

The predictive performance and reliability of the regression correlations (Eqs. (20)–(23)) are assessed using standard statistical measures, as summarized in Table 8. The coefficient of determination (R^2) values for all cases range from 0.9961 to 0.9996, indicating that more than 99% of the variability in the numerical data (Table 6) is accurately captured by the proposed regression models. Furthermore, the adjusted R^2 values (0.9940–0.9994) remain very close to the corresponding R^2 values, confirming that the models are free from overfitting and that all governing parameters contribute significantly to the prediction.

Table 8: Summary of statistical output for $\sqrt{Re_x}C_f$ and $\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}}$.

Statistical Output	$\sqrt{Re_x}C_f$		$\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}}$	
	UBS	LBS	UBS	LBS
RMSE	0.0152	0.0135	0.0165	0.0310
R^2	0.9961	0.9966	0.9996	0.9986
Adjusted R^2	0.9940	0.9947	0.9994	0.9978
F-statistic	483.49	547.90	4727.99	1334.73
p-value	$< 10^{-12}$	$< 10^{-12}$	$< 10^{-12}$	$< 10^{-12}$
Maximum Relative Error	0.0276	0.0298	0.0008	0.0012

The root mean square error (RMSE) values are found to be very small for both the skin-friction coefficient and the Nusselt number in the upper branch solution (UBS) and lower branch solution (LBS), demonstrating excellent agreement between the regression predictions and the computed numerical results. In addition, the maximum relative error remains within acceptable limits, being less than 3% for the skin-friction coefficient and of the order of 10^{-3} for the Nusselt number, which further validates the high accuracy and stability of the developed correlations. The statistical significance of the regression models is confirmed by the large F-statistic values, which vary from 483.49 to 4727.99, indicating that the overall models are highly significant. Moreover, the associated p -values are extremely small ($p < 10^{-12}$), well below the standard significance level, thereby confirming that the independent variables exert a statistically meaningful influence and are not due to random variation. From a physical perspective, the signs and magnitudes of the regression coefficients are in good agreement with the trends observed in the numerical analysis. The suction parameter (S) enhances the skin-friction coefficient due to the thinning of the velocity boundary layer and the corresponding increase in wall shear stress. The shrinking parameter (ξ) exhibits an opposing effect, reflecting its tendency to suppress the flow. The nanoparticle volume fraction (ϕ_{thnf}) significantly influences both momentum and heat transfer characteristics due to the improved thermophysical properties of the nanoparticles. Similarly, parameters such as the slip parameter (λ), radiation parameter (N_r), and Eckert number (Ec) exhibit behavior consistent with the underlying physical mechanisms governing the flow and heat transfer. Overall, the regression correlations demonstrate excellent statistical accuracy, strong physical consistency, and high predictive capability. Therefore, these models can be effectively employed as reliable surrogates to estimate the skin-friction coefficient and Nusselt number without the need for repeated numerical simulations, particularly in engineering design and optimization applications.

7 Conclusion

The present study investigates the flow and heat transfer characteristics of a Casson–Williamson trihybrid nanofluid over a permeable shrinking surface, accounting for velocity slip, quadratic thermal radiation, and viscous dissipation. The governing nonlinear partial differential equations were transformed into similarity equations and solved numerically using a boundary value approach. The analysis reveals the existence of dual solutions within a specific range of the governing parameters. A temporal stability analysis based on an eigenvalue formulation was carried out to determine the physically admissible solution. Furthermore, statistical regression analysis was employed to validate the numerical

results, confirming the model's accuracy and robustness.

The key findings of the study are summarized as follows:

- Dual solutions exist for certain ranges of suction and shrinking parameters, indicating multiple flow regimes.
- Stability analysis shows that the upper branch solution is stable and physically realizable, whereas the lower branch solution is unstable.
- Increasing the suction parameter enhances both the skin-friction coefficient and the Nusselt number due to the thinning of momentum and thermal boundary layers.
- Higher shrinking rates require stronger suction to sustain the boundary layer flow and avoid flow separation.
- The Casson parameter and Weissenberg number significantly affect the non-Newtonian behavior, altering velocity gradients and thermal distributions.
- Quadratic thermal radiation increases the temperature profile, highlighting the importance of nonlinear radiative effects in high-temperature applications.
- Viscous dissipation (Eckert number) contributes to additional heat generation, leading to higher thermal energy within the flow region.
- The trihybrid nanofluid exhibits superior heat transfer performance compared to mono and hybrid nanofluids due to enhanced effective thermophysical properties.
- Statistical analysis confirms excellent model accuracy, with high R^2 values, low RMSE, and significant F-statistics, indicating strong agreement between numerical and predicted results.
- The results provide useful guidance for the design of efficient thermal systems in engineering and biomedical applications involving complex non-Newtonian nanofluids.

References

- [1] Choi SU, Eastman JA. Enhancing thermal conductivity of fluids with nanoparticles. Argonne National Lab.(ANL), Argonne, IL (United States); 1995.
- [2] Eastman JA, Choi SUS, Li S, Yu W, Thompson LJ. Anomalously increased effective thermal conductivities of ethylene glycol-based nanofluids containing copper nanoparticles. Applied Physics Letters. 2001;78(6):718-20.
- [3] Subhani M, Nadeem S. Numerical analysis of micropolar hybrid nanofluid. Applied Nanoscience. 2019;9(4):447-59.
- [4] Ali B, Jubair S, Aluraikan A, Abd El-Rahman M, Eldin SM, Khalifa HAEW. Numerical investigation of heat source induced thermal slip effect on trihybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface. Results in Engineering. 2023;20:101536.
- [5] Amjad M, Farman M, Ali H, Waqar M. Numerical Study of Heat Transfer in Tri Hybrid Nanofluid Over a Stretching Sheet. Journal of Nanofluids. 2025;14(5):697-703.

- [6] Riaz S, Afzaal MF, Wang Z, Jan A, Farooq U. Numerical heat transfer of non-similar ternary hybrid nanofluid flow over linearly stretching surface. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*. 2024;85(23):4021-35.
- [7] Nagaraja B, Vidhya K, Almeida F, Kumar P. Numerical illustration of diffusive flow of blood-based tri-hybrid nanofluid generated by a curved stretching sheet using law of porosity. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*. 2025;86(16):5626-47.
- [8] Jamrus FN, Ishak A, Waini I, Khan U. Radiative influence on axisymmetric ternary hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary conditions over a nonlinearly permeable stretching/shrinking disk. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*. 2024;34(12):4333-61.
- [9] Alharbi AA. Thermal analysis of heat transport in a slip flow of ternary hybrid nanofluid with suction upon a stretching/shrinking sheet. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2024;54:103965.
- [10] Mandal G, Pal D. Mathematical modeling of entropy generation in MHD mixed convective Cu–Ag–Al₂O₃/H₂O tri-hybrid nanofluid over an exponential permeable shrinking surface with radiation and slip impacts: Multiple solutions with stability analysis. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals*. 2025;86(8):2588-616.
- [11] Mandal G, Pal D. Stability and multiple solutions of MHD-quadratic radiative tri-hybrid nanofluid flow in a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium over a rotating shrinking disk. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*. 2025.
- [12] Hafidzuddin E, Nazar R, Arifin N, Pop I. Boundary layer flow and heat transfer over a permeable exponentially stretching/shrinking sheet with generalized slip velocity. *Journal of applied fluid mechanics*. 2016;9(4):2025-36.
- [13] Casson N. A flow equation for pigment–oil suspensions of the printing ink type. In: *Rheology of Disperse Systems*. Pergamon Press; 1959. p. 84-102.
- [14] Williamson RV. The flow of pseudoplastic materials. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*. 1929;21(11):1108-11.
- [15] Patil PM, Kulkarni MR, Hiremath PS. Numerical study of Casson–Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with thermal radiation and chemical reaction. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat and Fluid Flow*. 2024;34(2):891-912.
- [16] Yousef N, Megahed AM, Ghoneim NI, Elsafi M, Fares E. Chemical reaction impact on MHD dissipative Casson-Williamson nanofluid flow over a slippery stretching sheet through porous medium. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2022;61(12):10161-70.
- [17] Abbas M, Qamar M, Khan M, Hussain S. Chemically reactive flow of Williamson nanofluid with nonlinear thermal radiation over an exponentially stretching/shrinking surface. *Journal of Radiation Research and Applied Sciences*. 2025;18(3):101630.
- [18] Gomathi N, Poulomi D. Dual solutions of Casson Williamson nanofluid with thermal radiation and chemical reaction. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*. 2025;86(15):5161-84.

- [19] Pooja M, Ramasekhar G, Narasimhamurthy S. Artificial neural network-based prediction of Casson tri-hybrid nanofluid flow over a curved stretching surface: Application to drug delivery. *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*. 2025;8(8):351.
- [20] Saleem M, Hussain M. Dual solutions of Williamson-Casson fluid over a heated exponentially shrinking surface with stability analysis: A novel Cattaneo-Christov heat flux model combination. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*. 2024;85(1):114-36.
- [21] Gomathi N, Poulomi D. Entropy optimization on EMHD Casson Williamson pentahybrid nanofluid over porous exponentially vertical cone. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2024;108:590-610.
- [22] Patil PM, Goudar B, Momoniat E. Casson-Williamson ternary hybrid nanofluid flow over a yawed cylinder with the impacts of multiple slips. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*. 2024;34(12):4181-205.
- [23] Nasir S, Sirisubtawee S, Gul T, Juntharee P, Alghamdi W, Ali I. Thermal characteristics of nonlinear convection and radiation for the flow of tri-hybrid nanofluids over stretchable surface with energy source. *Surface Review and Letters*. 2022;29(11):2250153.
- [24] Thriveni K, Mahanthesh B. Quadratic thermal radiation effects on nanofluid flow past a stretching surface. *European Physical Journal Plus*. 2020;135:792.
- [25] Mahanthesh B, Gireesha BJ, Gorla RSR. Nonlinear thermal radiation and heat source effects on nanofluid flow. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2021;123:105177.
- [26] Aarathi T, Reddy AS. Entropy generation due to a micropolar ternary hybrid nanofluid flow over a vertical stretching cylinder under quadratic thermal radiation: an artificial neural network approach for heat transfer analysis. *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*. 2025;8(8):1-28.
- [27] Shaw S, Samantaray S, Misra A, Nayak M, Makinde O. Hydromagnetic flow and thermal interpretations of Cross hybrid nanofluid influenced by linear, nonlinear and quadratic thermal radiations for any Prandtl number. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2022;130:105816.
- [28] Mandal G. Numerical stability of quadratic thermal radiative unsteady tri-hybrid nanofluid flow due to a contracting-rotating Riga disk. *Thermal Advances*. 2025:100048.
- [29] Wang C. Stagnation flow towards a shrinking sheet. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*. 2008;43(5):377-82.
- [30] Mahapatra TR, Nandy SK. Stability of dual solutions in stagnation-point flow and heat transfer over a porous shrinking sheet with thermal radiation. *Meccanica*. 2013;48(1):23-32.

- [31] Ghosh S, Mukhopadhyay S. Stability analysis for model-based study of nanofluid flow over an exponentially shrinking permeable sheet in presence of slip. *Neural Computing and Applications*. 2020;32(11):7201-11.
- [32] Zainal NA, Nazar R, Naganthran K, Pop I. Stability analysis of MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching/shrinking sheet with quadratic velocity. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2021;60(1):915-26.
- [33] Mandal G, Pal D. Stability analysis of radiative-magnetic hybrid nanofluid slip flow due to an exponentially stretching/shrinking permeable sheet with heat generation. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*. 2023;44(1):1349-60.
- [34] Kaswan P, Kumar M, Kumari M, Mandal G, Obalalu A. Stability and multiple solutions of ternary hybrid nanofluid in a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium over a stretching/shrinking surface. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*. 2025;150(13):10575-93.
- [35] Mandal G, Pal D. Impacts of binary chemical reaction with activation energy on MHD thermally radiating blood based hybrid nanofluid flow through shrinking-stenotic artery: Entropy generation and stability analysis. *Hybrid Advances*. 2024;7:100293.
- [36] Mandal G, Pal D. Impact of gold and silver nanoparticles on the thermally radiating MHD slip blood flow within the stenotic artery using stability analysis and entropy optimisation. *Pramana*. 2024;98(4):1-19.
- [37] Mahanta G, Parida C, Meher D, Shaw S. Entropy and thermal optimization on electromagnetic darcy–forchheimer trihybrid nanofluid flow with regression and sensitivity analysis: G. Mahanta et al. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*. 2025;150(18):14583-602.
- [38] Sindhu T, Jagadeeshkumar K. Entropy generation and regression analysis of unsteady Carreau ternary hybrid nanofluid flow with electromagnetic and thermal influences. *Discover Nano*. 2025;20(1):231.
- [39] Arpita B, Sharma RP, Saha UK. Sensitivity analysis of heat transfer in water-and kerosene-based trihybrid nanofluids in MHD Casson flow. *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*. 2025;8(8):354.
- [40] Alwawi FA, El-Sayed EA. Computational and regression analysis of EMHD Casson tri-hybrid nanofluid flow over a radiant Riga plate: Viscous dissipation, suction, and shape factor considerations. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*. 2025;17(8):16878132251370790.
- [41] Humane PP, Patil VS, Patil AB. Chemical reaction and thermal radiation effects on magnetohydrodynamic flow of Casson–Williamson nanofluid over a porous stretching surface. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*. 2021;235(6):2008-18.
- [42] Khan MR, Elkotb MA, Matoog R, Alshehri NA, Abdelmohimen MA. Thermal features and heat transfer enhancement of a Casson fluid across a porous stretching/shrinking sheet: Analysis of dual solutions. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2021;28:101594.

- [43] Rosseland S. *Astrophysik: Auf atomtheoretischer Grundlage*. Berlin: Springer; 1931.
- [44] Mahanthesh B, Mackolil J, Radhika M, Al-Kouz W, et al. Significance of quadratic thermal radiation and quadratic convection on boundary layer two-phase flow of a dusty nanoliquid past a vertical plate. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2021;120:105029.
- [45] Eswaramoorthi S, Sivasankaran S. Entropy optimization of MHD Casson-Williamson fluid flow over a convectively heated stretchy sheet with Cattaneo-Christov dual flux. *Scientia Iranica*. 2022;29(5):2317-31.
- [46] Khan KA, Vivas-Cortez M, Ahammad NA, Bushra H, Gamaoun F, Javed MF, et al. Unfolding some numerical solutions for the magnetohydrodynamics Casson-Williamson nanofluid flow over a stretching surface. *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering*. 2024;11(3):1-11.
- [47] Crane LJ. Flow past a stretching plate. *Zeitschrift für angewandte Mathematik und Physik*. 1970;21:645-7.
- [48] Jabeen S, Hayat T, Alsaedi A. Entropy generation optimization and activation energy in flow of Walters-B nanomaterial. *Scientia Iranica*. 2021;28(3):1917-25.
- [49] Arif M, Di Persio L, Kumam P, Watthayu W, Akgül A. Heat transfer analysis of fractional model of couple stress Casson tri-hybrid nanofluid using dissimilar shape nanoparticles in blood with biomedical applications. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13(1):4596.
- [50] Raju CSK, Sandeep N. Heat and mass transfer in MHD Casson fluid flow over a stretching sheet with slip effects. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2016;55(3):2045-54.
- [51] Cengel YA, Ghajar AJ. *Heat and Mass Transfer: Fundamentals and Applications*. 5th ed. McGraw-Hill; 2015.
- [52] Hayat T, Qayyum S, Alsaedi A. Influence of heat and mass transfer in viscoelastic fluid flow. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*. 2015;209:178-84.
- [53] Buongiorno J. Convective transport in nanofluids. *Journal of Heat Transfer*. 2006;128(3):240-50.
- [54] Mahapatra TR, Nandy SK. Effects of viscous dissipation on heat transfer over a stretching sheet. *Applied Mathematics and Mechanics*. 2011;32:1077-88.
- [55] Shampine LF. Vectorized adaptive quadrature in MATLAB. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 2008;211(2):131-40.
- [56] Sahoo A, Nandkeolyar R. Entropy generation and dissipative heat transfer analysis of mixed convective hydromagnetic flow of a Casson nanofluid with thermal radiation and Hall current. *Scientific Reports*. 2021;11(1):3926.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the physical model.

Figure 2: Variations of skin-friction coefficient for several values of ξ against S .

Figure 3: Variations of Nusselt number for several values of ξ against S .

Figure 4: Variations of skin-friction coefficient for NF, HNF and THNF against S .

Figure 5: Variations of Nusselt number for NF, HNF and THNF against S .

Figure 6: Dual velocity profiles for different We and β .

Figure 7: Dual temperature profiles for different We and β .

Figure 8: Dual temperature profiles for different Nr .

Figure 9: Dual velocity profiles for different λ .

Figure 10: Dual temperature profiles for different λ .

Figure 11: 3D plot of skin-friction coefficient against S and ξ .

Figure 12: 3D plot of Nusselt number against S and ξ .

8 Conflict of Interest

The authors confirm that personal or financial relationships had no impact on the studies mentioned in this paper.

9 Data Availability

All data generated or analysed during this study are freely available and also included in this article.

10 Funding Information

No funding was received for this research.